

Effect Of Ozonated Aloe vera Gel Application as an Adjunct to Scaling and Root Planning in the Treatment of Stage II Grade A Periodontitis Patients

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ABSTRACT

Ozonated Aloe vera gel is known for strong antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and enhanced wound healing properties. This combination can be used as an adjunct to mechanical debridement to improve periodontal health. Objective: To evaluate the effect of ozonated Aloe Vera gel application as an adjunctive therapy to scaling and root planing in the management of Stage II Grade A periodontitis patients. Methods: 30 stage II grade A periodontitis patients were divided into Group I (n=15; SRP + OA gel) and Group II (n=15; SRP + non-OA gel). Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), Probing Pocket Depth (PD), and Clinical Attachment Level (CAL) were recorded at baseline and 2 months post-operatively. Results: Baseline scores were comparable between both groups. A significant reduction ($p < 0.001^*$) was observed from baseline to 1 month and 2 months within each group. Intergroup comparison revealed no significant difference overall; however, a statistically significant ($p < 0.001^*$) gain in Clinical Attachment Level (CAL) was noted in Group I from baseline to 2 months compared to Group II. Conclusion: Both groups showed similar reductions in plaque and gingival inflammation; however, the OA group demonstrated greater CAL, highlighting its effectiveness as an adjunct in the treatment of periodontitis.

Keywords: Chronic Periodontitis, Herbal derivatives, Ozone, Root planning.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis causes inflammation, bleeding, clinical attachment loss (CAL), and marginal bone loss (MBL)¹ Gingival bleeding and tooth mobility are key indicators and may lead to tooth loss if untreated. Anaerobic Gram-negative bacteria in subgingival plaque drive disease progression, requiring professional plaque removal. Treatments include surgical and nonsurgical approaches, with scaling and root planning (SRP) as the standard. However, SRP alone cannot completely eliminate bacteria, particularly in furcations, interproximal spaces, root concavities, and deep pockets.²

Systemic or local antibiotics and topical antiseptics are often used alongside SRP to enhance treatment outcomes.³ Since bacterial products, immunological and inflammatory factors are involved in the

pathogenesis of periodontal disease, some products as adjunctive therapy can be used to help the healing process or controlling bacterial infection, and they can overcome the disadvantages of mechanical methods of plaque control.⁴ Due to the fewer side effects of medicinal herbs, some studies showed green tea, Cordiaverbenacea (a native plant of Brazil coasts) and Mikania laevigata, per se or in combination with SRP, can be beneficial in periodontitis treatment.⁵ Aloe vera is a cactus-like plant of Liliaceae family with about 360 species containing 75 active ingredients such as vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignins, saponins, salicylic acids, and amino acids. Aloe vera medicinal effect in vitro or on animal models has shown to have anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis and anti-bacterial effects.

Ozone is a potent antioxidant agent with antimicrobial activity due to the release of reactive oxygen species,

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

effectively targets a wide range of microbial pathogens, such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and protozoa. It can reduce the microbial burden in periodontal pockets, potentially improving clinical outcomes.⁶ Previous studies have observed that ozone has excellent biocompatibility with periodontal cells and gingival fibroblasts, and it may also benefit the host's metabolism and immune cell activity.⁷ The use of ozone as an antimicrobial could be very useful considering the pathogenetic action exerted by bacteria in the development and maintaining of periodontal inflammation. Ozone therapy offers a promising alternative to conventional broad-spectrum antiseptics like chlorhexidine in periodontal treatment. While both demonstrate antimicrobial efficacy against diverse pathogens, ozone presents distinct advantages due to its favourable safety profile and minimal toxicity. This characteristic makes it particularly valuable as an interim therapeutic option while targeted antimicrobial agents specific to periodontal pathogens continue to be developed.⁸

Taking into considerations of effectiveness of aloe vera and ozone the present study was planned to observe the clinical outcomes with placement of OA gel as an adjunctive to scaling and root planing (SRP).

Methods: A randomized, parallel-group, single-blinded clinical trial was conducted in the Department

of Periodontology at SIBAR Institute of Dental Sciences, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (Approval No: Pr.348/IEC/SIBAR/2024), and the trial was registered with the Clinical Trials Registry of India (CTRI/2024/09/074503). Prior to participation, the study protocol was thoroughly explained to all subjects, and written informed consent was obtained.

Sample size calculation: The sample size was determined using G*Power software (version 3.1.9.2), based on an effect size of 1.2, an alpha error probability of 0.05, and a power ($1-\beta$) of 0.80, ensuring an 80% probability of detecting a statistically significant difference between the groups. The calculation yielded a total sample size of 30 participants.

The study enrolled 30 systemically healthy individuals between 20 and 50 years of age, of both sexes, who were diagnosed with Stage II, Grade A periodontitis with probing pocket depth of ≤ 5 mm, Clinical attachment loss of 3-4mm and with no loss of teeth. Exclusion criteria included pregnant or lactating women, individuals with a known history of drug allergies, patients undergoing antibiotic therapy, and those with any form of tobacco use. The CONSORT diagram of the study design is given in Figure-1

Figure 1: CONSORT Flow diagram of the study

Evaluation criteria: Data were obtained by recording the Plaque Index (Silness and Løe, 1964), Gingival Index (Løe and Silness, 1963)⁹, Probing Pocket Depth (PPD), and Clinical Attachment Level (CAL).¹⁰ Periodontal parameters were measured using University of North Carolina -15 (UNC-15) periodontal probe (Hufriedy®IL, USA). A total of 30 patients diagnosed with Stage II Grade A periodontitis were included in the study. Participants were randomly divided into two equal groups: Group I (n=15): SRP + Ozonated Aloe vera (OA) gel and Group II (n=15): SRP + Non Ozonated Aloe vera (NOA) gel. Both the gels are taken into 5 ml syringes and were masked.

Procedure: At the baseline visit, a comprehensive clinical examination was performed for each participant, and all relevant clinical parameters were recorded. Subjects who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were randomly assigned into two groups: Group I and Group II. All participants underwent Phase I therapy, which included oral hygiene instruction and supragingival scaling. Following this initial therapy, under local anesthesia, participants underwent non-surgical periodontal therapy (NSPT), which involved SRP performed using ultrasonic (woodpecker®, Guilin, PRC) and hand instruments using area specific Gracey curettes (Hufriedy®IL, USA). The instrumentation was performed systematically across all affected sites until the root surfaces were rendered smooth and free of calculus and plaque retentive factors, thereby facilitating optimal conditions for periodontal healing and reattachment of the periodontal tissues. All procedures were conducted by a single calibrated operator (DP) to minimize inter-operator variability and maintain consistency in treatment delivery.

Group I received OA gel application as an adjunct to non-surgical periodontal therapy whereas Group II received NOA gel in conjunction with the same therapy. Additionally, they were advised not to brush near the gel-treated sites or use interdental aids during the initial post-treatment period. Following the

procedure, participants were given post-operative instructions, refrain from eating, drinking, or rinsing for at least 30 minutes post-application and to avoid chewing hard or sticky foods. They were also advised to avoid mechanical cleaning in the treated areas for the first 24 hours and the use of a 0.12% chlorhexidine mouth rinse twice daily for one week to aid plaque control and promote healing.

At two months (2M) post-operatively, all participants were recalled for re-evaluation of clinical parameters to assess the healing response and treatment outcomes. All measurements at baseline and 2M post-operative were performed by a single calibrated examiner (LG) who was blinded to the study design and group allocation. During each follow-up visit, oral hygiene instructions were reinforced to maintain optimal plaque control and ensure patient compliance.

Statistical analysis: All data were compiled and subjected to statistical analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to compute the mean and standard deviation (SD) for all clinical parameters in both groups. The normality of data distribution was assessed prior to analysis. For within-group comparisons from baseline to two months, the paired t-test was employed. For intergroup comparisons, independent t-test was used where data did not meet the normality assumption. A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The demographic characteristics of the study participants revealed that Group I consisted of 7 males and 8 females, while Group II comprised 8 males and 7 females. The mean age of participants in Group I was 45.2 ± 6.8 years, and in Group II was 47.1 ± 7.3 years. These findings indicate that both groups were comparable with respect to age and gender distribution, ensuring baseline homogeneity between the study populations (Table-1).

Table1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Groups

Variable	GROUP I (n=15)	GROUP II(n=15)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	45.2 ± 6.8	47.1 ± 7.3	0.452
Gender (Male:Female)	8:7	7:8	0.739

Within-group comparisons demonstrated a significant improvement in all clinical parameters over the 2-month evaluation period in both groups. In Group I, the PI decreased from 1.10 ± 0.10 at baseline to 0.70 ± 0.06 ($p < 0.001$), while Group II showed a reduction

from 1.08 ± 0.52 to 0.63 ± 0.37 ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, GI improved markedly, decreasing from 0.97 ± 0.29 to 0.52 ± 0.17 in Group I and from 0.94 ± 0.47 to 0.76 ± 0.41 in Group II, both changes being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$)(Table-2).

Table 2: Intra-group comparison of clinical parameters from baseline to 2months in using Paired t test

Parameter	Group	Time	N	Mean ± SD	P value
PI	I	Baseline	15	1.10 ± 0.10	<0.001*
		2M	15	0.70 ± 0.06	
	II	Baseline	15	1.08 ± 0.52	<0.001*
		2M	15	0.63 ± 0.37	
GI	I	Baseline	15	0.97 ± 0.29	<0.001*
		2M	15	0.52 ± 0.17	
	II	Baseline	15	0.94 ± 0.47	<0.001*
		2M	15	0.76 ± 0.41	
PPD	I	Baseline	15	5.16 ± 0.53	<0.001*
		2M	15	3.86 ± 0.39	
	II	Baseline	15	4.96 ± 0.43	<0.001*
		2M	15	3.94 ± 0.37	
CAL	I	Baseline	15	4.58 ± 0.56	<0.001*
		2M	15	3.21 ± 0.25	
	II	Baseline	15	4.50 ± 0.47	<0.001*
		2M	15	3.84 ± 0.42	

Paired t test; p-value ≤ 0.05 is statistically significant; * denotes significance

A marked reduction in PPD was observed in both groups, decreasing from 5.16 ± 0.53 to 3.86 ± 0.39 in Group I and from 4.96 ± 0.43 to 3.94 ± 0.37 in Group II ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, the CAL demonstrated a significant gain, improving from 4.58 ± 0.56 to 3.21 ± 0.25 in Group I and from 4.50 ± 0.47 to 3.84 ± 0.42 in Group II ($p < 0.001$). Overall, both treatment groups exhibited statistically significant intragroup improvements across all clinical parameters between baseline and the 2-month follow-up period(Table-2)

Intergroup comparison of the Plaque Index (PI) showed reductions in both groups (Group I: 1.10 ± 0.10 to 0.77 ± 0.06 ; Group II: 1.08 ± 0.52 to 0.63 ± 0.37), with no statistically significant difference between them ($p = 0.068$). In contrast, the Gingival Index (GI) exhibited a significantly greater reduction ($p = 0.047$) in Group I (0.97 ± 0.29 to 0.52 ± 0.17) compared to Group II (0.94 ± 0.47 to 0.76 ± 0.41) (Table 3).

Table3: Inter-group comparison of clinical parameters from baseline to 2 months between the groups using independent sample t test

Parameter	Group	N	Baseline (Mean ± SD)	2Months (Mean ± SD)	p-value
PI	I	15	1.10 ± 0.10	0.70 ± 0.06	0.068
	II	15	1.08 ± 0.52	0.63 ± 0.37	
GI	I	15	0.97 ± 0.29	0.52 ± 0.17	0.047*
	II	15	0.94 ± 0.47	0.76 ± 0.41	

PPD	I	15	5.16 ± 0.53	3.86 ± 0.39	0.577
	II	15	4.96 ± 0.43	3.94 ± 0.37	
CAL	I	15	4.58 ± 0.56	3.21 ± 0.25	0.000*
	II	15	4.50 ± 0.47	3.84 ± 0.42	

Independent sample t test; p-value ≤ 0.05 is statistically significant; * denotes significance

Probing Pocket Depth (PPD) decreased in both groups (Group I: 5.16 ± 0.53 to 3.86 ± 0.39; Group II: 4.96 ± 0.43 to 3.94 ± 0.37) with no statistically significant intergroup difference ($p = 0.577$). In contrast, CAL demonstrated a highly significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) in Group I (4.58 ± 0.56 to 3.21 ± 0.25) compared with Group II (4.50 ± 0.47 to 3.84 ± 0.42) (Table 3).

Discussion: Non-surgical periodontal therapy primarily relies on mechanical debridement through scaling and root planing (SRP) to eliminate subgingival biofilm and reduce periodontal inflammation. The adjunctive use of natural agents, such as Aloe Vera, has garnered clinical interest owing to its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties.¹¹ Herbs are a rich source of bioactive phytochemicals, many of which exhibit significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Modern therapeutic practice increasingly acknowledges plant-based medicines as valuable alternatives to synthetic pharmaceuticals due to their multi-targeted therapeutic potential, favorable safety profiles, and cost-effectiveness in clinical management.¹² Ozone therapy, an emerging adjunct in periodontal treatment, exerts its effects through reactive oxygen species, which help reduce microbial load, modulate immune responses, and enhance tissue repair by regulating cytokine activity.¹³ Moreover, the addition of ozone appeared to enhance Aloe Vera's therapeutic effects, providing superior anti-inflammatory and regenerative benefits. These results are consistent with existing evidence supporting the use of natural adjuncts in periodontal therapy, while also offering new insights into the synergistic potential of ozone when combined with herbal agents. Sanz et al. established that the cornerstone of periodontal therapy remains mechanical biofilm disruption via scaling and root planing (SRP).¹⁴ In the present study, both treatment groups, Group I (SRP + OA gel) and Group II (SRP+ NOA gel) demonstrated significant within-group improvements across all measured periodontal parameters over two months, reinforcing SRP's primary role in disease management.

A study by Verma et al. demonstrated that ozonated Aloe Vera gel exhibits antiplaque and anti-inflammatory effects comparable to 1% chlorhexidine. In the present study, Group II showed a greater reduction in Plaque Index (1.08 ± 0.52 to 0.50 ± 0.37) compared to Group I (1.10 ± 0.10 to 0.70 ± 0.06). This unexpected finding may be attributed to factors such as ozone concentration, gel consistency, or individual patient variation. Further research is warranted to optimize ozonated Aloe Vera formulations for more consistent clinical outcomes.¹⁵

Colombo et al. demonstrated that ozone gel, when used as an adjunct to SRP, significantly improves periodontal parameters, including Plaque Index (PI) and Gingival Index (GI), owing to its strong antimicrobial and oxygenating properties. In the present study, Group I exhibited greater plaque reduction compared to Group II, further supporting these findings and highlighting the potential benefits of ozone-enhanced Aloe Vera gel in nonsurgical periodontal therapy.¹⁶

A previous study by Nambiar et al. reported significant improvements in Clinical Attachment Level (CAL) and Probing Pocket Depth (PPD) when ozonated olive oil gel was used as an adjunct to SRP in chronic periodontitis. Similarly, the present study demonstrated greater CAL gain and PPD reduction in Group I compared to Group II over the two-month period. These findings support the enhanced therapeutic effect of ozone when combined with herbal gels, highlighting its potential benefit in managing Stage II periodontitis through improved clinical outcomes.¹⁷

According to Santos et al., adjunctive antimicrobial agents, such as Aloe Vera enhance mechanical debridement by targeting biofilm-associated pathogens, resulting in significant plaque reduction. However, their anti-inflammatory effects may be limited compared to host-modulating agents like OA. This aligns with our findings, where NOA demonstrated superior plaque control but a lesser

reduction in gingival inflammation compared to OA.¹⁸ Furthermore, Mukherjee K et al. emphasized that combining ozone with plant-based gels can provide dual benefits—broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity alongside Phyto therapeutic healing—making such combinations clinically valuable for the comprehensive management of periodontitis.¹⁹

While ozone therapy offers therapeutic benefits in periodontal treatment, its safety profile can vary considerably across formulations. Although gaseous ozone demonstrates potent antimicrobial effects, it carries notable risks, including respiratory toxicity and systemic complications such as rhinitis, headache, or severe cardiovascular effects. In contrast, ozone gel formulations, as used in the present study, provide comparable efficacy while offering a markedly improved safety profile, eliminating inhalation risks and retaining both antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.²⁰

The present study has several limitations. First, the sample size was relatively small, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Second, the short follow-up period may not fully capture the long-term effects of the adjunctive gels. Third, only clinical parameters—including PI, GI, PP), and CAL were evaluated; assessments of anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties were not included, which could have provided deeper insights into the gels' effectiveness. Finally, the study was restricted to systemically healthy patients, limiting the ability to evaluate the efficacy of the gels in medically compromised populations, such as patients with diabetes.

CONCLUSION

Our findings indicate that both ozonated and non-ozonated Aloe Vera gels, when used as adjuncts to SRP, lead to significant improvements in clinical periodontal parameters. However, ozonated Aloe Vera demonstrated superior outcomes in reducing gingival inflammation and enhancing clinical attachment. These results, supported by evidence from previous studies, suggest that Aloe Vera, particularly when combined with ozone, has considerable potential as an effective adjunct in nonsurgical periodontal therapy. Future research should focus on standardizing ozonated Aloe Vera

formulations, evaluating longer-term clinical outcomes, and elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying the synergistic effects of ozone and Aloe Vera.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors do not have any conflicts of interest related to this study.

REFERENCES

1. Savage A, Eaton KA, Moles DR, Needleman I A systematic review of definitions of periodontitis and methods that have been used to identify this disease. *J Clin Periodontol* 2009;36:458–467.
2. Alsakr, A.; Gufran, K.; Alqahtani, A.S.; Alasqah, M.; Alnufaiy, B.; Alzahrani, H.G.; Alahmari, A.A.; Alhumaidani, F.K.; Alhumaidani, R.K.; Althobiti, M.J. Ozone Therapy as an Adjuvant in the Treatment of Periodontitis. *J. Clin. Med.* 2023, 12, 7078.
3. Quirynen, M.; Teughels, W.; De Soete, M.; Van Steenberghe, D. Topical antiseptics and antibiotics in the initial therapy of chronic adult periodontitis: Microbiological aspects. *Periodontology* 2000,2002, 28, 72–90.
4. Preshaw PM, Taylor JJ. How has research into cytokine interactions and their role in driving immune responses impacted our understanding of periodontitis? *J Clin Periodontol.* 2011;38(s11):60–84.
5. Suchetha A, Bharwani AG. Efficacy of a commercially available multi-herbal formulation in periodontal therapy. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2013; 17: 193-197.
6. Hashim NT, Babiker R, Dasnadi SP, Islam MS, Chaitanya NC, Mohammed R, et al. The impact of ozone on periodontal cell line viability and function. *Curr Issues Mol Biol.* 2025 Jan 23; 47(2):72.
7. Nogales CG, Ferrari PH, Kantorovich EO, Lage-Marques JL. Ozone therapy in medicine and dentistry. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2008;9(4):75–84.
8. Gandhi KK, Cappetta EG, Pavaskar R. Effectiveness of the adjunctive use of ozone and chlorhexidine in patients with chronic periodontitis. *BDJ Open.* 2019 Nov 28; 5:17.

9. Loe H: The Gingival Index, the Plaque Index and the Retention Index System. *J Periodontol.* 1967; 38:610-6.
10. Loe H, Silness J. Periodontal disease in pregnancy. I. Prevalance and severity. *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica.* 1963; 21:533-51.
11. Ashifa N, Viswanathan K, Srinivasan S, Pavithran VK, Shankar S, Sundaram R, Kumar S, Anusha D. Clinical effectiveness of aloe vera gel as an adjunct to mechanical debridement in patients with periodontitis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Adv Periodontol Implant Dent.* 2025 Jan 20; 17(1):15-25.
12. Vo TTT, Chu PM, Tuan VP, Te JSL, Lee IT. The promising role of antioxidant phytochemicals in the prevention and treatment of periodontal disease via the inhibition of oxidative stress pathways: updated insights. *Antioxidants.* 2020; 9(12):1211.
13. Pardo A, Signoriello A, Brancato G, Brancato R, Messina E, Faccioni P, Marcoccia S, Nardi GM, Lombardo G. Effectiveness of Ozone Therapy in Non-Surgical Periodontal Treatment: A Meta-Analysis of Topical Applications. *Journal of Clinical Medicine.* 2025; 14(14):5124.
14. Sanz M, Beighton D, Curtis MA, Cury JA, Dige I, Dommisch H, et al. Role of microbial biofilms in oral health and disease. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2017;44(Suppl 18):S5–11.
15. Verma UP, Garg R, Kumar S, Mehrotra N, Verma P. Comparative evaluation of ozonated aloe vera and 1% chlorhexidine gel in periodontal disease: A clinical and microbiological study. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2020;24(6):521–525.
16. Colombo M, Gallo S, Garofoli A, Poggio C, Arciola CR, Scribante A. Ozone gel in chronic periodontal disease: a randomized clinical trial on the anti-inflammatory effects of ozone application. *Biology (Basel).* 2021;10(7):625.
17. Nambiar S, Malothu S, Karmakar S, Varkey A, Chandra D, Chava VK. Comparison of ozonated olive oil and chlorhexidine gel as an adjunct to nonsurgical periodontal therapy for the treatment of chronic periodontitis: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2022 Jul; 14(Suppl 1):S94-8.
18. Castro Dos Santos NC, Andere NMRB, Araujo CF, de Marco AC, Kantarci A, Van Dyke TE, Santamaria MP. Omega-3 PUFA and aspirin as adjuncts to periodontal debridement in patients with periodontitis and type 2 diabetes mellitus: Randomized clinical trial. *J Periodontol.* 2020 Oct; 91(10):1318-1327.
19. Mukherjee K, Amaranath BJ, Das N, Dhanai A, Pallavi K, Katiyar P. Efficacy of olive oil, ozonated olive oil, and chlorhexidine gel as an adjunct to scaling and root planing in chronic periodontitis: a clinical study. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2024; 16(Suppl 4):S3332–S3334.
20. D'Ambrosio F, Caggiano M, Acerra A, Pisano M, Giordano F. Is ozone a valid adjuvant therapy for periodontitis and peri-implantitis? A systematic review. *J Pers Med.* 2023; 13(4):646.

HOW TO CITE: Divya Pedapudi, Kishore Kumar Katuri, Lalasa Gaddam, Durga Prasad Malothu, Deepa Anumala, Ravindhranath Dhulipalla, Effect Of Ozonated Aloevera Gel Application as an Adjunct to Scaling and Root Planning in the Treatment of Stage Ii Grade A Periodontitis Patients, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 811-817. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17938016>

